

End-to-end Slicing of RAN based on Next Generation Optical Access Network

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Abstract—Due to their large diffusion, optical access networks represent a viable supporting infrastructure for mobile networks and services. The heterogeneity of services supported by mobile networks calls for the implementation of slicing mechanisms able to accommodate resources in all the involved network segments from the mobile user up to the core network.

In this work, we demonstrate a fully-functional and integrated 5G network deployment to satisfy real end-to-end slicing in next-generation access networks. We evaluate the impact of optical access network resources allocation mechanisms on slice performance in terms latency and jitter experienced by mobile users.

Index Terms—Slicing, Next Generation Access Network, RAN, SDN, PON

I. INTRODUCTION

Telecommunication networks have a distributed, shared architecture that is designed to forward traffic from one location to another. With the well-known mobile generations from first to fifth (1G to 5G), mobile networks have been experiencing a rapid technological advancement for more than 40 years. The current generation (i.e., 5G) is being implemented globally to replace the 4G specification and open up entirely new use cases for mobile networks that were previously restricted to landline connections. The flexibility that 5G technology brings introduces new issues that need to be solved. One of them is the next-generation Node B (gNB) high density required to cover uRLLC and eMMTC use cases.

To satisfy 5G network service demands such as dynamic Quality of service (QoS) requirements, operators must boost network capacity by deploying more RAN components (gNBs), which raises Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) and Operational Expenditure (OPEX), or by sharing the RAN, which allows operators to share CAPEX and OPEX expenditures and also enhance the mobile coverage [1]. RAN sharing can be defined as an approach in which the antenna, tower, power, mast, and backhaul equipment for the access network are shared by more than one network operator to provide different vertical services [2].

Network slicing is among the most essential components of 5G, provides a wide range of applications with different service demands through network virtualization [3]. Network slicing is the establishment of dedicated virtual network functions (VNF) with capabilities unique to the service or client across a shared network infrastructure [4] and it is realized

with the support of Network Function Virtualization (NFV). NFV offers these VNFs with a customizable, adaptable, and modular network environment [5]–[7].

The 5G Core (5GC) exploits its Service Based Architecture in a "cloud-native" manner. Slices are realized by NFV under the Network Slice Selection Function (NSSF) control. Each 5GC slice can be made up of a group of 5G core VNFs that are linked together to support a particular use case. One of the key features of 5G is Control and User Plane Separation (CUPS). It allows a 5G core system to be split into two parts: the Control Plane (CP) and the User Plane (UP). The CP is used as a common slice, whereas the UP is split into multiple customised slices with different bandwidth and latency requirements. The only UP 5G network function is User Plane Function (UPF) which is in charge of establishing and sustaining Packet Data Unit (PDU) sessions to route and send data packets to different external Data Networks (DNs). 5G UPFs can be sliced to accommodate different services in order to meet diverse QoS requirements.

Due to their high capillarity, Passive Optical Networks (PONs) represent an interesting supporting infrastructure for a variety of services with heterogeneous requirements (e.g., multimedia) [8], IoT, critical services, and nonetheless mobile networking. Thus, the adoption of network slicing in PONs may be beneficial from both business and network efficiency viewpoint. In [9], the authors highlight the issues that may occur in a shared access network serving a 5G Radio Access Network (RAN). A method to compute optimal virtual PON (vPON) slice configuration supporting uRLLC scenarios is proposed in [10] while in [11] slice management strategies in PONs via NETCONF are illustrated. In [12] the virtualization and isolation problems in RAN are studied by the authors. They setup a testbed to deploy dynamic and isolated RAN slices to deliver end-to-end slices to the end users, however they only manage to run a LTE testbed and not considered slicing with PON.

Integrated management of radio and optical access networks represents a viable solution to increase network efficiency, especially in slicing scenarios as discussed in [13]. The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate feasibility of a fully-functional and integrated 5G network deployment to satisfy real end-to-end slicing in next-generation access networks.

Fig. 1. Network Architecture

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider the reference architecture shown in Fig. 1 composed by three network segments, i.e., the RAN, the Optical Access Network (OAN), and the 5G Core. The OAN is a PON and is adopted as backhauling infrastructure for next-generation Node Bs (gNBs). The gNB is equipped with an Optical Network Termination (ONT) and the PON is also utilized as Fiber To The X (FTTx) infrastructure for other services such as residential and business connectivity and Internet of Things (IoT).

In order to deploy end-to-end slices, resources in the three considered network segments, have to be jointly allocated. To achieve such integrated resource allocation we consider a Management and Orchestration Framework which includes software defined controllers for the optical access and mobile networks and a network orchestrator. A Slice Manager element is responsible to map requirements of different slices into ad-hoc configurations of the network segments and to coordinate the network controllers and the network orchestrator throughout the slice life-cycle.

The network controllers are responsible to implement resource allocation strategies able to meet the desired slice performance. At the mobile core segment the network orchestrator is responsible to deploy 5G core functions such as Access Management Function (AMF), User Plane Function (UPF), Network Repository Function (NRF), and Session Management Function (SMF) that constitute the slices at mobile core level. This also allows to place UPF in different physical locations, according to the Service Level Agreement or the user's requirements. An UPF deployed at the edge may guarantee very low latency capable to serve ultra reliable and low latency communication (uRLLC) while an UPF deployed at central office or at a cloud provider may help cutting down CAPEX and OPEX at the cost of increased latency.

As the OAN may be shared with other customers (i.e., residential customers) isolation on the optical link is crucial to

provide desired SLA for the service running at 5G network. 5G traffic on that segment includes user's data and control traffic to manage the radio network so demanding for isolation and prioritization. Such traffic differentiation is achieved at the PON by adopting different bandwidth allocation strategies such as: (i) Request-Grant based access which leverages Dynamic Bandwidth Assignment procedures to exploit statistical multiplexing and increases network efficiency at the price of a larger experienced latency; (ii) *Expedited Forwarding* which gives to a particular slice the possibility to utilize a reserved amount of bandwidth in a Grant-free fashion in order to reduce experienced latency.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the considered experimental setup primarily consisting of three different parts that are the RAN, OAN and CN.

Radio Access Network (RAN): The RAN is deployed by using OpenAirInterface (OAI) open-source RAN software stack [14]. Then we deployed two OAI-based UEs (*UE 1* and *UE 2*) using two different physical machines. The UEs are connected to the RAN by using National Instrument X310 Universal Software Radio Peripherals (USRPs). The UE side USRPs are connected with the gNB side USRP through a two-way signal splitter/combiner with SubMiniature version A (SMA) connectors as shown in Fig. 2. This allows to evaluate multi-user connection with the single gNB.

On the other end, the OAI gNB is configured with Single – Network Slice Selection Assistance Information (S-NSSAI) list to support two different Slice/Service Type (SST) and Slice Differentiator (SD) values to evaluate the RAN slicing scenario.

Optical Access Network (OAN): The OAN segment in our setup is deployed in between the RAN and CN. It is realized by utilizing commercial Calix Axos E7-2 NG-PON2 that provides a configurable NETCONF API useful to configure isolation

Fig. 2. Experimental Setup

and network traffic rules at runtime to implement dynamic slicing. To provide the traffic differentiation and isolation at the forwarding plane we implemented a slicing mechanism based on IEEE 802.1Q Virtual Local Area Networking (VLAN). The 802.1Q standard also specifies a 3 bit Priority Code Point (PCP) to select traffic type. It is worth noting that 802.1Q does not specify how to implement traffic type differentiation based on PCP.

The Calix Axos E7-2 is able to instruct the ONT to differentiate traffic based on VLAN tags and PCP. This way, services that needs high priority and low latency can use VLANs to get their Service-Level Agreements (SLAs) fulfilled. We configured the OAN to treat the traffic belonging to Slice 1 (associated to VLAN 112 and PCP 7) as *Expedited Forwarding* — to be transmitted from the ONT to the OLT without applying request-grant mechanism in order to reduce latency. The traffic belonging to Slice 2 is associated with VLAN 113 and PCP 3 and is transmitted in a *Best Effort* manner — via traditional request-grant based on dynamic bandwidth allocation.

The mechanism to ensure low latency to a specific slice through the whole network is as follows:

- 1) The gNB applies a VLAN tag and PCP to each packet going towards to the 5G CN, for each UE, by utilizing virtual ethernet interfaces.
- 2) The ONT uses the PCP to apply forwarding policies such as *Expedited Forwarding* or *Best Effort*
- 3) The traffic flows through the OAN to the 5G CN, where the CN slicing contains two different User Plane Functions (UPF) associated with two different VLAN tags as shown in Fig. 2

The forwarding policies at the OLT can be configured in a dynamic way with help of Slice Manager (NETCONF) as shown in Fig. 1.

Core Network (CN): The OAI-based 5G Core is implemented in a scalable manner that makes it simple to adapt to the requirements of various 5G use-cases [15]. In this, different Network Functions (NFs) are implemented to provide services — the Control Plane (CP) and User Plane (UP) functions are separated to enable independent scaling. Here, Network Slice Selection Function (NSSF) decides on the acceptable NSSAI, and sets Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF) to serve the UE. As shown in Fig. 2, each Slice is associated with three different NFs — Network Repository Function (NRF), Session Management Function (SMF), and User Plane Function (UPF) — and their selection is mainly based on the S-NSSAI with the help of NSSF.

The container (Docker) based 5G Core with all the required NFs are deployed, specifically two UPFs (i.e., Slice 1 and Slice 2) are associated with the two UEs while running the experiments to guarantee isolation and enhance slice performance.

In order to evaluate the impact of different resource allocation strategies of the OAN on the slice performance we perform delay measurements: (i) between gNB and Core (i.e., optical access delay); (ii) between the UEs and Core (i.e., end-to-end delay). To perform round trip time measurement we send ICMP packets with a ping interval of 10ms.

Fig. 3 shows the optical access delay measured between gNB and Core for the two slice under consideration. It can be noticed that *Expedited Forwarding* allocation strategy adopted for Slice 1 allows to reduce the delay in the PON by the 80% compared to the Slice 2 which is served in a *Best Effort* strategy. In fact, the optical access latency measured for Slice 1 is 0.25ms average while the one measured for Slice 2 is around 0.85ms. Such reduction is due to the absence of request-grant procedure for Slice 1 whose transmission opportunities in upstream are reserved in advanced allowing the ONT to transmit in a grant-free fashion, thus, reducing queuing of

Fig. 3. PON latency for different slices

Fig. 4. UEs to Core (UPFs) latency for different slices

packets at the ONT.

Fig. 4 shows end-to-end latency measurements for the two slices. As can be noticed, the end-to-end delay measured for Slice 1 is significantly reduced compared to Slice 2. Such delays include contribution of the RAN together with the one of the OAN. Fig. 4 shows that the improvement of performance introduced by resource reservation in the optical access network can be observed not only in terms of latency reduction but also in terms of end-to-end jitter reduction. This is explainable by the fact that packets belonging to Slice 1 are not queued at the ONT. This significantly reduces delay variations which can be up to 10ms as measured for Slice 2.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper we presented a real implementation of an end-to-end slicing of RAN based on optical access network. We utilize a commercial NG-PON2 for the backhauling of the mobile traffic and deploy container based sliced core network elements. We evaluate the impact of the proposed VLAN and

PCP based slicing of the optical access segment. Results show that the proposed slicing mechanism is able to significantly reduce the experienced latency while offering reduced jitter to mobile users belonging to a specific slice.

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